

EVALUATION OF OPERATIVE DANGERS FOR PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM LIVER DISEASES.

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Abstract

Cirrhosis increases perioperative morbidity and mortality. We present a review of mortality data, perioperative morbidity, risk assessment, and treatment of cirrhosis patients with non-hepatic surgery. We found multiple cirrhotic patient perioperative outcomes studies after a thorough search. Our narrative review included research design, perioperative mortality by Model for End-stage Liver Disease (MELD), surgical technique, and Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) class score. Studies reported; depending on liver dysfunction, perioperative mortality is two to 10 times greater for cirrhosis patients. Liver transplantation or other alternatives to surgery should be considered for compensated cirrhosis patients. Due to a lack of evidence, case studies and professional opinions guide the perioperative care of cirrhosis patients. Current risk calculators are inadequate. Cirrhosis patients' perioperative mortality and morbidity depend on liver failure, medical comorbidities, the kind and complexity of the surgery, whether elective or emergency, and the period between diagnosis and operation. Risk assessment and perioperative management clinical research contain severe problems that require more study. These shortcomings severely restrict the analysis.

Keywords

Cirrhosis; Risk assessment; Review; Morbidity; Mortality

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